

The Significance of A. Urinboev's Research in the Study of the Historical Heritage of the Turkish People

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Abstract:

The article provides brief comments on the history of the Uzbek historian's introduction into scientific circulation of handwritten sources that are important in the study of the history of the Turkic peoples.

Keywords: Turks, people, Amir Temur, manuscript, translation.

Today studying the historical and cultural heritage of the Turkic peoples, uniting the peoples of the world is one of the urgent issues. The Institute of Oriental Studies under the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan keeps manuscript sources that help to study the history of the Turkic peoples in depth. Among them, there are also sources introduced into scientific circulation by Doctor of History A. Urinboev, which are analyzed below. The research conducted by A. Urinboev on important sources in the study of the history of the Turkic peoples was studied in groups.

1. A. Urinboev selflessly served in the translation of Abu Ali ibn Sina's "Laws of Medicine" from Arabic into Uzbek and Russian languages, and his services in introducing sources related to the history of Uzbekistan, Uzbek medicine, and Uzbek pharmacology into scientific circulation.

2. A. Urinboev, as a historian-scientist, worked with the manuscript sources that shed light on the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid state, a topic that faced great obstacles in the Soviet era, and withstood the arduous tests of the autocratic regime. served as a source.

3. A. Urinboev's introduction of Abdurakhman Jami's autographs written to Navoi into scientific circulation became the basis for serving as a pure source not only within the history of Uzbekistan, but also for such disciplines as philosophy, political science, social science, and Uzbek literature.

4. Unique manuscripts related to the study of the history of the Kokand khanate - such works as "Tarikh jadidayi Tashkand", "Khulosat-ul akhvol" He has been a beacon for many Kokan historical scientists in our country with his research on the history of Kokan.

5. It was found that A. Urinboev's services were also great in preparing and printing the work "History of Bukhara" written by Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Ja'far Narshahi.

1. In 1954, the first edition of Abu Ali Ibn Sina's famous work "Medical Laws", recognized as a treasure in the field of medicine, was published. The second edition was published in 1983. In the 1954 and 1983 editions of these books, A. Urinboev is mentioned as a translator [1.1.].

2. In 1960, A. Urinboev carried out a large-scale scientific research, which was discussed in detail in the second chapter of the dissertation, in the paragraph entitled "Introduction of Abdurazzokh Samarkandi's work "Matlai sa'dayn va majma-i bahrayn" by A. Urinboev into scientific circulation." Because Asomiddin Urinboev's candidate's dissertation was carried out on the scientific research work of Abdurazzoq Samarqandi entitled Indian travel book (1442-1444) [2.1.].

A. Urinboev also mentions valuable information about the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid State in his article "Envoy, Traveler, Geographer" published in 1962 [3.1.]. It also contains information about the personality of Abdurazzoq Samarkandi and his career as an ambassador, but his notes as a tourist and geographer are analyzed in detail.

3. One of the major researches carried out by A. Urinboev during the Soviet period was related to the letters of Abdurahman Jami, which was covered in detail in the 2nd chapter of the dissertation. In 1965, A. Urinboev published his researched works in a book [6.1.].

4. A. Urinboev published the article "Neizvestnaya rukopis po isturii Kokandskogo khanstva" in 1957. This research work was carried out based on the work entitled "Summary of the Kokan Khanate". [7.1.]. A. Urinboev's research on this work written in the Persian-Tajik language and personal manuscript extracts were discussed in the third chapter of the dissertation.

5. "History of Bukhara" by Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Ja'far Narshahi was translated from Persian-Tajik into Uzbek by A. Rasulov. In preparing this book for publication, the "Introduction" part was written by Asomiddin Urinboev [8.1.].

In conclusion, it can be said that there are more than 400 studies conducted by A. Urinboev in the study of the history of the Turkic peoples, and the best ones have been analyzed in this article.

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